

Example Workflows for Federal Funding Administration at US Institutions

Public Version

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Introduction

As part of our project, “Investigating ‘reasonable costs’ to achieve public access to federally funded research and scientific data”, supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. 2330827, Invest in Open Infrastructure investigated how institutions were responding to new public access policies associated with United States federal funding. This document includes sample workflows from 23 institutions in the United States, gathered through surveys and interviews. These workflows are simplified versions of actual practices, intended to capture points where public access considerations are addressed. These workflows represent a snapshot of the institution’s processes as of January 2025.

This publication was created as part of the project, “Investigating ‘reasonable costs’ to achieve public access to federally funded research and scientific data”, supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. 2330827. For more information and additional outputs of this project, please visit: <https://investinopen.org/data-room/reasonable-costs/>

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Cary Institute federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Key

- Terminator
- Start and end points
- Process
- An action or function
- ◇ Decision point
- Document
- The input/output of a document
- Researcher/PI
- Library
- Office of Sponsored Programs (OSP)
- IT and Research Computing (I T/RC)
- Science Admin
- ▲ Required step
- Process intervention/input

Awareness

- Library**
Conduct monthly funding-related workshops, e.g. developing a DMSP, creating metadata
- Library**
Maintain Libguides with information about policy compliance and resources for researchers, including policy compliance, DMSP, and other resources
- OSP**
Hold group meeting to share policies, practices, training
- OSP**
Track federal policies and disseminate information
- VP of OSP, Chief of Science, VP of IT, Library director**
Participate in Working Group to discuss implementation of OA policies

Formal Grant Reporting

- Researcher: Submit grant RPPR reports
- OSP: Communicate and work with PIs to prepare, review compliance requirements, submit technical reports (Annual, Interim, Final, or Project Outcomes) and any additional required reports (Invention/Patent reports, Equipment Reports, etc.) as per award terms; record and track reports
- Researcher: Submit final grant report
- OSP: Prepared and review financial reports to ensure compliance with terms of the award; record and track reports

Dartmouth College federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Grand Valley State University federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Indiana University Bloomington federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Michigan State University federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Middlebury College federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Northwestern University federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Pennsylvania State University federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Key

- Terminator
- Start and end points
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- An action or function
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- ▭ Document
- The input/output of a document
- University Libraries
- Central Processing Office (CPO)
- Senior Vice President for Research (SVPR)
- Strategic Interdisciplinary Research Office (SIRO)
- Institute for Computational and Data Sciences (ICDS)
- Data Commons
- Colleges/Centers (Coll/Ctr)
- ▲ Required step
- Process intervention/input

Additional abbreviations

DMSP - Data Management and Sharing Plan
 IR - Institutional Repository

Awareness

- Library Offer trainings**
- Library Develop LibGuides**
- SVPR Communicate significant changes**
- SVPR Communicate significant changes**
- Administrative Council on Research**
Share information about policies and requirements, host faculty list servs
- Office of Research Protections Education and Training Office**
Provide ongoing training on compliance and other topics
- Data Commons Offer trainings outreach, education**

Pepperdine University federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Purdue University federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Investigating reasonable costs to achieve public access to federally funded research and scientific data

State University of New York at Oswego federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

University of Chicago federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

University of Minnesota federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

College of William & Mary federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Yale University federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Institution A federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Institution B federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Institution C federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Institution D federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Key

- Terminator
- Start and end points
- Process
- An action or function
- Decision point
- Document
- The input/output of a document
- Researcher/PI
- Libraries
- Office of the Vice Chancellor for Research (OVCN)
- Research and Sponsored Programs (RSP)
- Human Research Protection Program (HRPP)
- Information Technology (IT)
- Data Science Institute (DSI)
- Open Source Program Office (OSPO)
- Center for Translational Research (CTR)
- Department/School/College/Division (Dpt/S/C/Div)
- Departmental Research Administrator (DRA)
- School/College/Division Administrator (S/C/Div Admin)
- Required step
- Process intervention/input

Additional abbreviations

- DMSP - Data Management and Sharing Plan
- IRB - Institutional Review Board
- NSF - National Science Foundation
- NIH - National Institutes of Health

Awareness and General Guidance

- Libraries/DSMIT (planned):** Maintain Data Catalog to support discovery, sharing, and tracking of resources.
- OVCN:** Convene working group to coordinate response to Nelson and NIH data sharing policy.
- Libraries:** Conduct lab/group training on ethics, qualitative data sharing, publishing, Open Access.
- IT:** Provide information on cybersecurity and data management for OVCN, Libraries, RSP.
- Libraries/RSP:** Outreach to PIs with NIH funding to encourage attending trainings and compliance with new requirements.
- IT (Dpt):** Provide information and guidance about IT policies and services.
- OSPO:** Provide guidance for open source projects.
- DSI:** Create policies.

Institution E federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

Institution F federal research funding workflow

Simplified workflow, current as of January 2025

